

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 76

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 76

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 76:0 For the choir director; on stringed instruments. A Psalm of Asaph, a Song.</p> <p>Psa. 76:1 God is ^aknown in Judah; His name is ^bgreat in Israel.</p> <p>² His ^{1a}tabernacle is in ^bSalem; His ^cdwelling place also is in Zion.</p> <p>³ There He ^abroke the ¹flaming arrows, The shield and the sword and the ²weapons of war. ³Selah.</p> <p>Psa. 76:4 You are resplendent, ¹More majestic than the mountains of prey.</p> <p>⁵ The ^astouthearted were plundered, ¹They sank into sleep; And none of the ²warriors could use his hands.</p> <p>⁶ At Your ^arebuke, O God of Jacob, Both ^{1b}rider and horse were cast into a dead sleep.</p> <p>⁷ You, even You, are ^ato be feared; And ^bwho may stand in Your presence when once ¹You are angry?</p> <p>Psa. 76:8 You caused judgment to be heard from heaven; The earth ^afeared and was still</p> <p>⁹ When God ^aarose to judgment, To save all the humble of the earth. Selah.</p> <p>¹⁰ For the ^{1a}wrath of man shall praise You;</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">Psa. 76:1</p> <p style="text-align: center;">לְמִנְצַחַת בְּנִגְיֹנֹת</p> <p>מִזְמֹר לְאַסָּף שִׁיר : ² נֹדֵעַ בְּיְהוּדָה אֱלֹהִים בְּיִשְׂרָאֵל גָּדוֹל שְׁמוֹ : ³ וַיִּהְיֶה בְּשָׁלֹם סִכּוֹ וּמַעֲוֹנָתוֹ בְּצִיּוֹן : ⁴ שָׁמָּה שָׁבַר רֶשֶׁפִי־קִשְׁת מִגֶּן וַחֲרָב וּמִלְחָמָה סֶלָה : ⁵ נָאֹר אֶתָּה אֲדִיר מִהַרְרֵי־טָרֶף : ⁶ אֲשֶׁתוֹלְלוּ אַבְיָרֵי לֵב נָמּוּ שָׁנְתָם וְלֹא־מָצְאוּ כָל־ אֲנָשִׁי־תַיִל יְדֵיהֶם : ⁷ מִנְעַרְתֶּךָ אֱלֹהֵי יַעֲקֹב נִרְדָּם וַרְכָב וְסוּסִים : ⁸ אֶתָּה אֲנֹרָא אֶתָּה וּמִי־יַעֲמֵד לְפָנֶיךָ מֵאִז אֲפָף : ⁹ מִשָּׁמַיִם הִשְׁמַעְתָּ דִּין אֶרֶץ יִרְאָה וְשָׁקְטָה : ¹⁰ בְּקוֹם־לְמִשְׁפַּט אֱלֹהִים לְהוֹשִׁיעַ כָּל־עַנְוֵי־אֶרֶץ סֶלָה : ¹¹ כִּי־תַחַמַת אָדָם</p>

With a remnant of wrath You will gird Yourself.

Psa. 76:11 ^aMake vows to the LORD your God and ^bfulfill *them*;

Let all who are around Him ^cbring gifts to Him who is to be feared.

¹² He will cut off the spirit of princes; He is ^{1a}feared by the kings of the earth.

תוֹדֶךָ שְׂאֲרֵית חֵמַת תַּחְזָר :
נִדְרֶיךָ וְשִׁלְמוֹ לַיהוָה ¹²
אֲלֹהֵיכֶם כָּל־סְבִיבָיו יוֹבִילוּ
שֵׁי לַמּוֹרָא : ¹³ יִבְצֵר רִוְחַת
נְגִידִים נוֹרָא לְמַלְכֵי־אֲרֶץ :

References

Psalm 76:1

^aPs 48:3

^bPs 99:3

Psalm 76:2

¹Lit *shelter*

^aPs 27:5; Lam 2:6

^bGen 14:18

^cPs 9:11; 132:13; 135:21

Psalm 76:3

¹Lit *fiery shafts of the bow*

²Lit *battle*

³*Selah* may mean: *Pause, Crescendo* or *Musical interlude*

^aPs 46:9

Psalm 76:4

¹Or *Majestic from the mountains*

Psalm 76:5

¹Lit *They slumbered their sleep*

²Lit *men of might have found their hands*

^aIs 10:12; 46:12

Psalm 76:6

¹Lit *chariot*

^aPs 80:16

^bEx 15:1, 21; Ps 78:53

Psalm 76:7

¹Lit *Your anger is*

^a1 Chr 16:25; Ps 89:7; 96:4

^bEzra 9:15; Ps 130:3; Nah 1:6; Mal 3:2; Rev 6:17

Psalm 76:8

^a1 Chr 16:30; 2 Chr 20:29, 30; Ps 33:8

Psalm 76:9

^aPs 9:7, 8; 74:22; 82:8

Psalm 76:10

¹Lit *wraths*

^aEx 9:16; Rom 9:17

Psalm 76:11

^aEccl 5:4-6

^bPs 50:14

^c2 Chr 32:23; Ps 68:29

Psalm 76:12

¹Lit *awesome to*

^aPs 47:2

Targum

Psa. 76:1 For praise, as a psalm; a psalm composed by Asaph, a song. ² God has become known among those of the house of Judah; his name is great among those of the house of Israel. ³ And his sanctuary has come to be in Jerusalem, and the dwelling of the house of his holy presence is in Zion. ⁴ When the house of Israel did his will, he made his presence abide among them; there he broke the arrows and bows of the Gentiles who were making war; he made forever the shields and battle-lines of no account. ⁵ Bright [and] awful are you, O God, acclaimed from your sanctuary; the kings who dwell in the mountain fortresses, the place where their spoil is gathered, will tremble in your presence. ⁶ The mighty in heart have stripped from them the weapons of war; they have slumbered in their sleep; and all the men of might have not been able to grasp their weapons in their hands. ⁷ At your rebuke, O God of Jacob, the chariots have fallen asleep, and the cavalry have been disabled. ⁸ You are awesome, you are God; and who will stand before you from the time your anger becomes strong? ⁹ From heaven you proclaimed judgment on the land of the Gentiles; the land of Israel was afraid [and] became silent. ¹⁰ The righteous say, "Let God arise for judgment with the wicked, to redeem from their hands all the meek of the earth forever." ¹¹ When you are angry at your people, you show mercy to them, and they will give thanks to your name; but the remainder of fury that is left to you, out of the wrath that you showed, you will gird on to destroy the Gentiles. [ANOTHER TARGUM: For when your anger grows strong against your people, they will repent and give thanks to your name, and you turn from anger; but against the remnant of the Gentiles you will gird on the instruments of anger.] ¹² Make vows and fulfill [them] in the presence of the LORD your God, all you who dwell around his sanctuary; let them bring offerings to his awesome temple. ¹³ He will diminish the arrogant spirits of the leaders; [he is] dreadful to all the kings of the earth.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

The LORD's majesty is now concealed in the shrouds of exile. The future triumph of the LORD over Gog and Magog will signal the return of Divine prestige. The LORD's glory will gradually spread until it is recognized worldwide. Divine protection will envelop Jerusalem, the LORD's dwelling place.

Verse one

To the Sefirah Netzach who grants victory through the art of music, a psalm, a song of Asaf.

Verse three

The original name of Jerusalem was Salem. Jerusalem is on the top of Mount Zion.

When His tabernacle was in Salem and His dwelling-place in Zion.

Verse ten

When God arises to judgment, it is to bring salvation to all the humble of the earth. Meditate on this verse.

Verse twelve

Midrash says that every Jewish soul that will ever live on the earth was in the valley of Mount Sinai when the LORD asked the people if they would accept His Torah. When

they accepted the Torah the LORD said that he would always protect them. This is the vow of all Jewish people.

But as far as you, vow, and fulfill your vows to the LORD your God, while all those round about Him bring tribute to Him as to One to be revered.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

